

Sl. No.	m.p. °C	%S Found (Calcd.)	%inhibition of germination at 1000 ppm	
			<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	47	10.54 (10.38)	70	48

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Flavonoids and other Constituents of

Indigofera hetrantha

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THE plant *Indigofera hetrantha* (wild) belonging to Leguminosae was collected from Gulmarg, Kashmir in June and was identified in the herbarium of the Botany Department, Kashmir University. The sister species of *Indigofera hetrantha* were found to contain toxic nitro compounds^{1,2} of insecticidal activity³. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to investigate this plant for its chemical composition.

Experimental

The dried plant material (12 kg) was extracted by percolation with ethanol. After removal of the

solvent *in vacuo* at 40° the residue (100 g) was partitioned between 2% aq. citric acid and ether to give a basic and a non-basic fraction. The non-basic fraction was fractionated by standard methods into neutral (20 g), acidic (15 g) and phenolic (6 g) fractions.

The phenolic fraction was chromatographed over silica gel (60-100 mesh). Elution with CHCl_3 , CHCl_3 -MeOH afforded IH_4 , IH_5 and IH_6 which were purified by re-column chromatography and preparative paper chromatography (Whatman No. 3, 15% HOAc).

The acidic fraction on chromatography over silica gel using C_6H_6 - CHCl_3 (1:3) as the eluent gave IH_7 which was purified by recrystallization.

The neutral fraction on chromatography over silica gel using light petrol, petrol- C_6H_6 , C_6H_6 as the eluents afforded IH_1 , IH_2 and IH_3 .

Refrigeration of acidic solution of the basic fraction gave an alkaloidal precipitate (300 mg). The tlc examination of this fraction revealed the presence of several compounds but could not be worked further because of the small amount.

Results

IH_4 : Yellow needles, m.p. 347-8°, M^+ , 270 agreed with elemental analysis of $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6$. The compound was identified as apigenin⁴ by uv, ir, nmr, m.m.p. The structure was further confirmed by its conversion to tri-acetate, m.p. 186°.

IH_5 : Yellow needles crystallized from EtOH, m.p. 261°, M^+ , 284 agreed with elemental analysis of $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$. The compound was identified as acacetin^{5,6} by co-tlc, m.m.p. and superimposable ir. Acetylation with Ac_2O /py gave a di-acetate, m.p. 203-5° further confirming its structure.

IH_6 : Yellow needles, m.p. 234-6°, M^+ , 464. The compound was isolated by preparative paper chromatography and gave an olive-green colouration with FeCl_3 . It was identified as isoquercitrin⁷ by uv, ir, nmr and m.m.p. On acid hydrolysis it gave quercitrin⁸, m.p. 313-16° and glucose confirming its structure.

IH_7 : It was identified as ursolic acid¹⁰ (150 mg), m.p. 242-4°. Its ir in KBr pellet showed the following absorption bands: ν_{max} 3450, 2950, 2890, 1685, 1450, 1030 and 990 cm^{-1} . MS: M^+ , 456. Treatment with Ac_2O /py gave O-acetyl ursolic acid, m.p. 268-270°. Direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p, ir) with an authentic sample confirmed the identity.

IH_1 and IH_2 could not be processed further due to their small amounts.

IH_3 : A white crystalline solid, m.p. 135-6°, was found to be β -sitosterol⁹ by co-tlc and m.m.p.

This appears to be the first record of the isolation of these compounds from this species.

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Chemical Constituents of *Eucalyptus citriodora* Roots

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EUCALYPTUS *citriodora* (F : Myrtaceae) is distributed¹ in India, Australia and many other countries. An essential oil (0.5-2.0%) is obtained from its leaves which is used in soap perfumery and as a source of citronellal. *Eucalyptus*² is used in the treatment of catarrhal states of bronchopulmonary mucous membrane, intermittent and septic fevers, diphtheria, whooping cough etc. Earlier examination showed the presence of oil and flavonoids in the leaves³⁻⁶ while the gum⁷ contained ellagic acid and flavonoids.

The present note deals with the chemical examination of the roots of *Eucalyptus citriodora*. The roots (3 kg) were extracted with hot acetone and alcohol separately. The acetone extract, on column chromatography over silica gel, gave six compounds (A-F). Compound A (β -sitosterol) crystallised from chloroform-methanol as colourless needles (50 mg), m.p. 136°, $[\alpha]_D - 34.5^\circ$ (CHCl_3). Co-TLC and m.m.p. with an authentic sample confirmed its identity⁸. Compound B (Betulinic acid) crystallised from methanol as silky needles (500 mg), m.p. 312-14°, $[\alpha]_D + 9^\circ$ (CHCl_3). It responded to L.B. test and formed an acetate, m.p. 286-88°. Identity established by m.m.p. with an authentic sample of betulinic acid⁹, co-tlc and superimposable ir.

Compound C (ursolic acid) crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (200 mg), m.p.

288-90°, $[\alpha]_D + 69^\circ$ (CHCl_3) and gave +ive L. B. test (pink $\rightarrow$ blue). Acetate, m.p. 245-46°, $[\alpha]_D + 57^\circ$ (CHCl_3). It was identified as ursolic acid¹⁰ by m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir.

Compound D (7-O-methylaromadendrin) crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH as light pale flat needles (2.0 g), m.p. 187-88°, $[\alpha]_D + 30^\circ$ (MeOH) and gave a transient purple to brown colour with FeCl_3 and +ive Zn/HCl test. Acetate, m.p. 136-37° ($\text{M}^+ 428$). It resembled in all respect with authentic 7-O-methylaromadendrin⁷ (ir, uv, nmr and mass). Compound E (aromadendrin) crystallised from methanol-benzene as colourless needles (800 mg), m.p. 247-48°, $[\alpha]_D + 25.5^\circ$ (MeOH) ($\text{M}^+ 288$). Acetate, m.p. 80-82°. It was characterised as aromadendrin⁷ by ir, uv, nmr, mass and by direct comparison with an authentic sample (co-tlc, m.m.p.). Compound F (fustin) obtained as colourless solid from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (250 mg), m.p. 213-15°, gave green colour with FeCl_3 and +ive Zn/HCl test. Acetate, m.p. 149-51°. It was identified as fustin¹¹ by ir, uv, nmr and by direct comparison with an authentic sample (co-tlc and m.m.p.).

Thus the occurrence of β -sitosterol, betulinic acid, ursolic acid, aromadendrin and 7-O-methylaromadendrin is noted for the first time in the roots of a *Eucalyptus* species and fustin for the first time in *Eucalyptus*.

No single compound could be isolated from alcohol extract.

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